

TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE: DIFFICULTIES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract: This article discusses main problems faced in teaching English as foreign a language (TEFL), including pronunciation errors, grammatical difficulties, lack of practice and exposure to English in daily life. It also highlights how native language affects learners` pronunciation and their overall learning process. Additionally, the study provides some effective solutions for these issues, for instance, conducting specialized pronunciation classes with native speakers, doing exercises related to grammar, as much as possible, integrating English into everyday activities to be more fluent and articulate.

Key words: TEFL, pronunciation skills, stress, shadowing, grammar rules, syllable, digraph, Duolingo, BBC Learning English, Ted Talks, YouTube tutorials.

Undoubtedly, English has been the main language in education, business, communication, and even networks. In terms of education, learning English is one of the most important aspects of study for those lives in countries where English is not the primary language. Despite the global importance of English, teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL) presents various challenges for both educators and learners.

First and foremost, one of the main concerns are language barriers and pronunciation issues. Obviously, English and Uzbek differ significantly in many aspects. For example, many English learners struggle with pronouncing the digraph "th" because of its absence in their native language. In phonetics, "th" is pronounced as either the voiceless in "think", or the voiced in "this". As it is enunciated differently in contrasting context, learners find it difficult to master.

Another major issue is word stress. In the Uzbek language, the last syllable of the word is highlighted, such as in "bola"(a child), while native English speakers do not stress the final part of the word in the same way. As a result, many learners grapple with pronouncing word endings correctly. As seen in the past tense forms like "worked" and "learned". Additionally, there are some words which are not fully pronounced. For instance, when enunciating the word "star", the final "r" is omitted in certain accents. It sounds like "sta". Naturally, it makes learning process more challenging for students.

One of the ways which can help to solve this problem is engaging in conversation with native speakers as they are more fluent and provide useful techniques to improve pronunciation. Moreover, an interesting technique called

"Shadowing" can be another effective approach to learning the correct pronunciation of certain words in English. At the same time, it is both enjoyable and beneficial to watch short segments of various films for improving pronunciation and listening skills.

Another significant challenge in learning English is achieving proficiency in its complex grammar rules. While English is domain language all over the world, researches show that its grammar is quite difficult to master and remains major weakness for learners. For instance, second-language learners struggle with English tenses. Unlike Uzbek, which has only three tenses-past, present and future- English has twelve main tenses in various categories. In turn, it results in incorrect use of tenses and students lose their confidence in real-life situations. Misuse of tense and other grammatical structures may lead to misunderstandings which discourage students from actively participating in conversations. In addition, irregular verbs present another challenge for non-native speakers as some verbs undergo significant changes like "go-went-gone", "eat-ate-eaten", "write-wrote-written". However, some verbs simply take the "ed" ending to convert into past tense and past participle such as "work-worked", "listen-listened", "ask-asked". In these kinds of situations many students face challenges which hinder them from mastering English grammar.

As a solution, studies suggest various strategies, including interactive grammar exercises and using online resources. Practicing grammatical tasks by memorizing and reciting grammar rules for at least two hours a day can be a good way to achieve high level of English grammar. Moreover, it is more beneficial if it is supervised by professional English teachers as they can help correct mistakes and provide clear explanations. Besides, in today's technologically advanced era it is possible to go online quickly and find online resources which allow students to expand their knowledge and provides exercises to improve their grammar skills.

The third major challenge in studying foreign language is limited exposure to English in students' daily lives. While students spend most of their time with learning foreign languages, in their everyday life they do not have a chance to interact with everyone in English, because in society they are required to communicate in their native language. Furthermore, if students attend schools where instruction is conducted in their mother tongue, they have fewer chance to express their thoughts in second language they are learning. In turn, it may lead to a loss of confidence while speaking in English, and their fluency may start to decline over the time. Moreover, many students exhibit reluctant when it

comes to speak in English, as it requires them think and articulate their ideas simultaneously. Especially, in this case they start to make grammatical mistakes, like misuse of tenses, articles and grammar structures making it difficult for them to express their ideas clearly and effectively.

To overcome these challenges, researches provide different solutions can help to achieve fluency and proficiency in second language. One of them is encouraging students to surround themselves with English. They can watch English movies, listen to podcasts, read books in English, which helps them to understand English idioms, phrases and English culture, as well. Furthermore, creating an English-speaking environment is another interactive way of practicing English. To be exact, they can form a study group where members interact each other only in English. This not only build confidence but also improves social skills. Coupled with this, attending English-speaking events such as debates, workshops, or online webinars can be efficient. Besides, students can apply online and interactive learning tools, such as Duolingo, BBC Learning English, Ted Talks, or YouTube tutorials, which provide structured and flexible language practice, in their everyday activities as they can use them anytime and anywhere they want.

In conclusion, learning a foreign language as a second or third language is never an easy task for students. There are a lot of challenges commonly faced in this process like pronunciation difficulties, complex grammar, and limited exposure to language. Even so, these obstacles can be overcome by immersive learning, structured practice, and use of digital resources. Although learning English requires dedication and hard work, following strategic learning methods significantly help to master it. By integrating English into daily life and actively engaging in language practice students can transform challenges into opportunities, ultimately achieving high level of fluency and confidence in the language.

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